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- 08.00.02 Makroiqtisodiyot
- 08.00.03 Sanoat iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.04 Qishloq xo'jaligi iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.05 Xizmat ko'rsatish tarmoqlari iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.06 Ekonometrika va statistika
- 08.00.07 Moliya, pul muomalasi va kredit
- 08.00.08 Buxgalteriya hisobi, iqtisodiy tahlil va audit
- 08.00.09 Jahon iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.10 Demografiya. Mehnat iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.11 Marketing
- 08.00.12 Mintaqaviy iqtisodiyot
- 08.00.13 Menejment
- 08.00.14 Iqtisodiyotda axborot tizimlari va texnologiyalari
- 08.00.15 Tadbirkorlik va kichik biznes iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.16 Raqamli iqtisodiyot va xalqaro raqamli integratsiya
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МУНДАРИЖА

Инвестиции в образование – путь к устойчивому развитию.....	11
Синдаров Шерзод Эгамбердиевич, Розиматов Санжарбек Косимжон угли	
Rentabellik – biznes modelining iqtisodiy samaradorligining o‘lchovi sifatida.....	14
Normo‘minov Temurbek Sheraliyevich	
“Hududgazta’minot» AJda amalga oshirilgan loyihalar samarasi.....	19
Ergashev Muhibbek Aslam o‘g‘li	
Sug‘urta kompaniyalarida sug‘urta zaxiralari hisobini takomillashtirish.....	25
Najimova N.	
AQSH va xitoy tashqi savdosining rivojlanish tendensiyalari va miliy iqtisodiyotimizga ta’siri.....	29
Rahimboyeva Begoyim Doniyor qizi	
Baliqchilik xarajatlari va olingan mahsulotlar hisobini tashkil etishni takomillashtirish.....	36
Aitimbetov Amirbek Qoishibekovich	
O‘zbekistonda banklar faoliyatida raqamlashtirish loyihalarini tatbiq etishni qo‘llab-quvvatlash samaradorligini oshirish.....	43
Maxsadaliyeva Maftuna Tohir qizi	
Tijorat banklarida muammoli kredit (npl) qarzdorliklarini undirish jarayonlarini takomillashtirish istiqbollari.....	50
Ko‘makov Shavkat Norboevich	
Xodimlarga munosib mehnat sharoitlari yaratishning iqtisodiy samarasi.....	57
Tuychiyev Dusmurod Tuychiyevich.	
Korxonalarining innovasion faoliyatini boshqarish vositalarini shakllantirishning zaruriy shartlari.....	63
Akramboyev Azizbek Rustamjon ug‘li	
Mamlakatimizda turizm sohasida oliy ma’lumotli kadrlar tayyorlashni boshqarish xususiyatlari.....	69
Ochilov Akram Odilovich, Xamidova Mo‘tabarxon Abdumalik qizi	
Sug‘urtada investitsiya muhitini tashkil etish.....	76
O‘tashev Jahongir Burxonovich	
Forms and models of familyeconomy.....	82
Fayziyeva Mashhura Qosimovna	
Oliy ta’lim muassasalarida kreativ yondashuv strategiyalarini ishlab chiqish mexanizmlari.....	88
Rahimova Kutlibeka Ergashevna	
Построение интегрированной системы управления затратами предприятий.....	95
Алиева С.С.	

Роль средств массовой информации и коммуникации в развитии образования механизmlari.....	100
Алиакбарова Рушанабону Муродуллаевна	
Концептуальные основы повышения эффективности производства в национальной экономике Республики Узбекистан.....	106
Рахматова Наргиза Агзамовна, Нурмухаммадов Лазизбек	
Tijorat banklarida xalqaro pul o'tkazmalarini rivojlantirish yo'llari.....	116
Sodiqov Baxtiyor To'raqulovich	
Temir yo'l tarmog'ini rivojlantirishning tashkiliy-iqtisodiy mexanizmi.....	125
Nasimov Shavkat Vasievich	
Tijorat banklarining kichik biznes subyektlarini kreditlash amaliyotini takomillashtirish yo'llari.....	132
Jalilov Baxodir Amiralievich	
Ekoturizmni rivojlantirishda ekologiyani muhofaza qilish: barqaror kelajak sari yo'l.....	138
Tirkacheva Farangiz Sur'at qizi	
O'zbekistonda xizmat ko'rsatish tarmoqlarini rivojlantirishda xorij tajribasi.....	145
Salomov Temurbek Boburmirzo o'g'li	
Bozor iqtisodiyoti sharoitida ishsizlik va inflyatsiya darajasini pasaytirish muammolari.....	152
Kamil Sharipov	
Sanoat korxonalarida mehnat sifati va samaradorligini oshirishda inson resurslarini boshqarish.....	159
Ergashev R.X., Ochilov A.O., Turaqulov O.O.	
Banklar likvidligi va kapitallashuv darajasining bank kredit kanali samaradorligiga ta'siri.....	164
Absalamov Akram Tolliboyevich	
O'zbekistonda raqamli iqtisodiyotning rivojlanish tendensiyasi.....	173
Davronov Jahongir Ma'sud O'g'li	
O'zbekiston iqtisodiyotida xizmatlar sohasining o'rni va uni yanada rivojlantirish yo'nalishlari.....	178
Berdiyev Anvar Abduraxmonovich	
Jamoat transporti xizmatlarining rivojlanishida olimlarning qarashlari.....	183
G'iyosidinov Boburbek Baxtiyor o'g'li	
Eco-marketing approaches for promoting green building materials through digital storytelling platforms.....	190
Koziyev Jalaluddin Alisher o'g'li	
Korxonada inson kapitalini rivojlantirish tizimi va konsepsiyasini takomillashtirish imkoniyatlari.....	197
Hamrokulov M.O.	

Роль инноваций в развитии электронной коммерции и цифровой экономики.....	207
Умарходжаева Зайнабхон Нодирхон кизи	
Korxonalarni qo‘llab quvatlashni moliyaviy mexanizmlarini takomillashtirish xorijiy davlatlarda misolida.....	211
Z.T.Mirzayev	
Tijorat banklari tomonidan uy-joylar qurilishini moliyalashtirishda qo‘llaniladigan usullar.....	221
Ziyayev Azamat Mirza o‘g‘li	
O‘zbekiston respublikasida auditorlik faoliyatining tashkiliy-huquqiy asoslari.....	229
Abdullaev Xurshidjon Nazrullo o‘g‘li	
Kosmik monitoring natijalari orqali raqamli qishloq xo‘jaligini boshqarishning zamonaviy jihatlar.....	239
Kamoliddin Madrahimov Ro‘zimbayevich	
Yengil sanoat korxonalarida eksport va import operatsiyalari hisobini takomillashtirish.....	247
Rasulova Zilola Abdig‘opparovna	
O‘zbekiston oliy ta‘lim muassasalarida talabalarga stipendiya va professor-o‘qituvchilarga ish haqi to‘lashning moliyaviy menejmentga ta‘siri.....	256
M.M.Tashxodjaev.	
« Понятие «туристский потенциал региона» : его характеристика и роль в социально-экономическом развитии дестинаций»	264
Очилов Акрам Одилович, Усманова Азиза Баходировна, Туракулов Ойбек Одил оглы	
Barqaror iqtisodiy rivojlanishni ta‘minlash.....	272
Muxamedjanova Gulzoda Odilovna	
Soliq yuki soliq tizimining qanchalik samarali ekanligini aniqlovchi muhim mezon.....	278
To‘lakov Ulug‘bek Toshmamatovich	
Yaponiya iqtisodiyotining jadal rivojlanishi sabablari.....	287
Artikova Shoxida Ilyasovna	
Soliq imtiy ozlarining samaradorligini baholash mezonlari.....	292
Akbarov Akmalxon Akrom o‘g‘li	
Xizmat ko‘rsatish sohasini samarali rivojlantirishda raqamli texnologiyalarning roli.....	298
Mamurjon Abdivoxidov Avazxon o‘g‘li	
O‘zbekistonda raqamli iqtisodning shakllanishida aholi turmush arovonligining yaxshilanishi va bandligining ta‘minlanishi.....	307
Djurayeva Ruxsora Nematilloevna	
Investitsiya jozibadorligini oshirish yo‘llari.....	314
Olimbekov Odilbek Saidmurodovich	
Temir yo‘l tarmog‘ini rivojlantirishning tashkiliy-iqtisodiy mexanizmi.....	322
Nasimov Shavkat Vasievich	

Oliy ta'limni moliyalashtirishning ilmiy-nazariy asoslari.....	330
Yo'ldoshev Jahongir To'raboevich	
Iqtisodiyot va ekologiya muvozanati: barqaror taraqqiyotga yondashuv.....	337
Turdiyeva Iroda Ismoil qizi	
Kosmik monitoring natijalari orqali raqamli qishloq xo'jaligini boshqarishning zamonaviy jihatlari.....	342
Kamoliddin Madrahimov Ro'zimbayevich	
Zamonaviy sharoitda biznesning pr faoliyati maqsadi.....	350
Ergasheva Fotimaxon Ibragimovna	
Raqamli iqtisodiyot sharoitida Tijorat banklarning qimmatli qog'ozlar bozoridagi faoliyati istiqbollari.....	355
Niyozmetov Doniyor Rejabbayevich	
Tijorat banklarining kichik biznes subyektlarini kreditlash amaliyotini takomillashtirish yo'llari.....	361
Jalilov Baxodir Amiralievich	
Инвестиции и их место в экономическом развитии страны.....	367
Махамаджанов Мухаммадали Музаффарович	
Global o'zgarishlar sharoitida raqamlashtirishning bank tizimiga ta'siri: muammo va yechimlar.....	373
Kutliyev Dilshod Orifovich	
Mintaqada mehmonxona xo'jaligida investitsiya samaradorligiga ta'sir etuvchi omillar.....	382
Jasur Berdiyev	
Mintaqa transport-logistika xizmatlari samaradorligini oshirish mexanizmlari va ularni takomillashtirish.....	387
Nargiza Eshqobilova	
Tadbirkorlik faoliyatini davlat tomonidan tartibga solish va qo'llab-quvvatlash tizimi.....	392
samaradorligini baholash usuli	
Amonov Mehriddin Oromiddinovich	
Bank moliyaviy aktivlari - iqtisodiyotning tomiri sifatida.....	399
Mamarajabov Bobur Abduxakimovich	
Integration of trade marketing and e-commerce: how to combine online and offline sales channels.....	403
Mamatkulova Shoiri Jalolovna	
Audit tekshiruvini rejalashtirishda ilg'or xorij tajribasi qo'llash imkoniyatlari.....	408
Akromov Shohrux Shuhrat o'g'li	
O'zbekiston yashil Iqtisodiyotining o'rni va uni rivojlantirish, shuningdek, yashil energetika.....	419
Sultonov Sirojiddin Normurolovich	
Biznes faoliyatini rivojlantirishga ta'sir etuvchi moliyalashtirish manbalari.....	427
Adilov Sherzot Shamilevich	

Soliq qonunchiligini raqamli iqtisodiyot sharoitiga moslashtirish.....	433
Imomova Muhabbat Volnazarovna	
Turizm sohasida madaniy meros obyektlaridan foydalanishning nazariy, uslubiy va konseptual asoslari.....	441
Raupov G‘ayrat Soyibovich	
“Raqamli tafovut” (digital divide) yondashuvi asosida destinatsiya jozibadorligini baholashning “raqamli tafovut indeksi” metodikasi.....	449
S.R. Bobokalonov	
O‘zbekistonda issiqlik energetikasini barqaror rivojlantirishda energetik tekshiruvlarni amalga oshirish strategik yo‘nalishlarini takomillashtirish.....	458
Saitkamolov Muxammadxo‘ja Sobirxo‘ja o‘g‘li	
Sog‘liqni saqlash tizimini rivojlantirishda “klaster” modelidan foydalanish samaradorligi.....	469
Ubaydullayev Bekmurod Muborakovich	
Зарубежный опыт повышения качества жилищно-коммунальных.....	476
услуг и его применение в узбекистане	
Икромжон Йигиталиев	
Sanoat korxonalarini boshqarishda innovatsion strategiyaning ilmiy-nazariy jihatlari.....	483
Xusanova Malohat Mengnoronovna	
Kichik biznes va xususiy tadbirkorlikni innovatsion rivojlantirish xususiyatlari.....	491
Abdulxakimov Sirojiddin Nurboy o‘g‘li	
Ijtimoiy turizm subyektlarini identifikatsiyalashning ayrim jihatlari.....	500
Rasulov Sherzod Ashirovich	
Tijorat banklari tomonidan loyihalarni moliyalashtirishning intensivligini oshirish.....	507
Abduraimova Nigora Abdugapparovna	
Soliq tizimi modernizatsiyasining konseptual asoslarini takomillashtirish.....	513
Nomazov Baxrom Bobomuradovich	
Yashil iqtisodiyotni ta’minlashda oziq-ovqat xavfsizligining nazariy asoslari va uni baholashga ta’sir etuvchi ko‘rsatkichlar tahlili.....	520
Samiyeva G.T.	
Korxonalarda innovatsion-investitsion faoliyatni tashkil etishning dunyo tajribasi.....	529
Taraxtiyeva Gulmira Kulbayevna	
Kichik biznes muhiti va uning o‘zgarishi omillari.....	537
Xasanboeva Naima Xasanboevn, Rashidov Rahmatullo A’lojonovich	
Совершенствование нормирования оборотных средств предприятий сферы услуг.....	543
Сайфиддинов Илхом Файзиддинович	
Xo‘jalik yurituvchi subyektlar investitsiya loyihalarini moliyalashtirish tahlili.....	549
Baxramov Abdulaziz Baxtiyorovich	
Mamlakatimiz iqtisodiyotining rivojlanishida aholi mehnat migratsiyasining ahamiyati.....	555
Djurayev Olimjon Narkulovich, Quziboyeva Nargiza Hamro qizi	

Kichik biznesni rivojlantirishni integral baholash.....	561
Israilov Rustam Ibragimovich	
Marketing tadqiqotining asosiy xususiyatlari va bank kredit bozori segmentatsiyasi.....	568
Razzoqov Nozim Abdiroziqovich	
Совершенствование учета ремонта основных средств в нефтеперерабатывающих.....	573
предприятиях республики узбекистан	
Атабаева Замирахон Абдужалиловна	
Soliq tushumlarini shakllantirish ko'rsatkichlari asosida soliq salohiyatini baholash usullari.....	580
Jo'raev Husan	
O'zbekistonda bozor iqtisodiyoti sharoitida menejmentning ahamiyati va roli.....	587
Berdiev Temurbek Maxmudullo o'g'li	
Inson kapitaliga investitsiya kiritish va undan foydalanish bo'yicha xalqaro tajriba.....	594
Abdikarimov Islombek Ibragimovich	
Tijorat banklarining qimmatli qog'ozlar bozorida investitsiya faoliyatining muhim jihatlari.....	605
Abiyev Davron Ilxomovich	
Milliy hunarmandchilik mahsulotlarini sotuviga ta'sir qiluvchi omillar tahlili.....	611
Ravshanova Gulchexra Ravshanovna	
Frilanserlik faoliyatini tashkil etish va rivojlantirish bo'yicha xorijiy davlatlar tajribalari.....	616
Lutpidinov Shuxrat Zakirdjanovich	
Kapital bozorini rivojlantirishda investitsiyaning o'rni.....	624
Mo'minov Shohijahon Suyun o'g'li	
Fond bozori orqali investitsiyalarni jalb etishni takomillashtirish	628
G'aniyev Axrorjon Norboy o'g'li	
“Hisob siyosatlarini, hisoblab chiqilgan baholardagi o'zgarishlar va xatolar” standartining qo'llanilishi.....	637
Mamajonov Akramjon Turgunovich	
Yuk tashuvchi avtotransport korxonalarida xizmat ko'rsatishning xususiyatlari.....	644
Ergasheva Muxabbat Abdusamatovna	
Mamlakatimiz iqtisodiyotining rivojlanishida aholi mehnat migratsiyasining ahamiyati.....	650
Djurayev Olimjon Narkulovich, Saidakbarov Jamshid Nematullo o'g'li	
Основная характеристика внебиржевого рынка ценных бумаг.....	656
Юлдашев Жамшид Аббарович	
Innovatsion boshqaruvning rivojlangan davlatlarda hududiy rivojlanishni boshqarish.....	665
bo'yicha tajribasi	
Muminov Fazliddin Xusniddin o'g'li	
Tasvirlarni ko'p yadroli signal prosessorlarida parallellashtirish algoritmlari.....	672
Samiyeva Maftuna	

Agrosanoatda kooperatsiya: xarakat va xarajatlar zanjirlarining uzviy muammolari.....	679
Ermatov Musojalil Komilovich	
O'zbekistonda inflyatsiyaga qarshi kurashishda samarali yo'llarni qo'llash choralari.....	684
Jumayev Muzaffar Mahmud o'g'li	
Qoraqolpog'iston respublikasida kichik biznes va tadbirkorlik faoliyatining iqtisodiy.....	689
ko'rsatkichlari tahlili Raimova Durdona Durdibay qizi	
Madaniylashgan qishloq xo'jaligi ekinlarining yovvoyi ajdodlaridan samarali.....	695
foydalanishning zarurati Xolliyev Sherali Baxtiyorovich	
O'zbekistonda yoqilg'i-energetika korxonalari faoliyatini soliqqa tortish mexanizmini.....	700
Takomillashtirish Xomidov Tuyinboy	
The relevance and need to improve the management of higher education institutions.....	706
Raxmonov Azizbek Abdullajonovich	
Oilalarning ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy rivojlanishida nazariy yondashuvlarning jamiyat taraqqiyotidagi o'rni va ahamiyati.....	712
Imomnazarov Hasan Ixtiyor o'g'li	
Tijorat banklarida depozit operatsiyalarini rivojlantirish imkoniyatlari.....	720
Xursanova Gulshan Ravshan qizi	
Audit tekshiruvini rejalashtirishda ilg'or xorij tajribasi qo'llash imkoniyatlari.....	726
Akromov Shohrux Shuhrat o'g'li	
Yashil bandlikni rivojlantirishning ilmiy asoslari.....	737
Mirzakarimova Muyassarxon Muminovna	
Iqtisodiyotni jadal rivojlantirish sharoitida sanoat korxonalari xodimlarini boshqarishning dolzarb masalalari.....	749
Jo'raeva Nodiraxon Qurbonovna	
Сфера туризма и значение инвестиционной деятельности в ее развитии.....	757
Уткиржан Ахмедов	
Антикризисное управление на малых и средних фирмах (Европейский опыт)	764
Жиянов Бахриддин Ибрагимович	
Aksiyadorlik jamiyatlarida konsolidatsiyalashgan kapital o'zgarishi to'g'risida hisobot.....	770
tuzishning muommo va istiqbollari Eshonqulov Azamat Abdiraximovich	
Hududlarda kichik biznes va xususiy tadbirkorlikni rivojlanib borish tendensiyalari tahlili.....	775
Jo'rayev Lazizjon Egamberdievich	
Tijorat banklarida kredit portfeli risklarini boshqarishdagi muammolar va innovatsion.....	785
yondashuvlar Jurayeva Muhabbatxon Maxmudjon qizi	

Erkin iqtisodiy zonalarda loyiha boshqaruvini tashkil qilish.....	792
Matluba Soyibova, Dinara Abdikarimova	
O‘zbekiston mintaqalarida sanoat tarmog‘ini rivojlantirishning hududiy jihatlar.....	797
Matniyazova Iqboloy Baxramovna	
Mamlakatimizda marketingning rivojlanish istiqbollari: muammo va yechimlar.....	806
Mirzaeva Intizor Ergashevna	
O‘zbekiston chakana bank xizmatlari rivojlanishi va tijorat banklarining samaradorligiga ta’siri.....	816
Tursunova Yulduz Xojayor qizi	
Aholi ish bilan samarali bandligining iqtisodiyot sohalari va tarmoqlari tarkibidagi o‘zgarishlarga.....	824
bog‘liqligi Alisher Tuychiyev Jurayevich, Yuldasheva Samarbonu	
Korxonalarda qaror qabul qilish masalalari.....	829
Ubaydullayev Lutfulla Xabibullayevich	
Buxgalteriya hisobida majburiyatlar va ularni tan olish mezonlari.....	835
Boltaev Abror Sayitmuradovich	
Tadbirkorlik sub’ektlariga ko‘rsatiladigan moliyaviy hisob-kitob xizmat turlarini.....	841
takomillashtirish yullari Abdurazakova Nargiza Rixsibaevna	
Aktivlar menejmenti tizimida amortizatsiya siyosati va uni muvozanatlashgan moliyaviy.....	845
barqarorlikni ta’minlashdagi o‘rni Kurbonov Xayrilla	
Aksiyadorlik jamiyatlarining moliyaviy resurslarini samarali boshqarish yo‘llari.....	855
Xolboev Sayfullo Narzullaevich	
Qoraqalpog‘iston respublikasida aholini ichimlik suv ta’minoti va oqova suv xizmatlari.....	861
bilan ta’minlash masalalari Xalmuratov Kallibek Joldasbaevich	
Kichik biznes va xususiy tadbirkorlik subyektlariga moliyaviy xizmatlar ko‘rsatishni takomillashtirish.....	871
G‘anieva Nozima Alijon qizi	
Pulli avtomobil yo‘llari loyihalari: ilg‘or tajribalar va ularni o‘zbekistonda qo‘llash.....	876
imkoniyatlari Rashidov Boburbek	
O‘zbekiston sug‘urta bozorini ekonometrik modellashtirish.....	881
Mirzayev Bobur Soyibjonovich	
Qishloq xo‘jaligi korxonalarida kapital qo‘yilmalar hisobining xususiyatlari.....	887
Baxriyev Muxiddin Sheraliyevich	
Davlat ehtiyojlari uchun tovarlar xarid qilishning ilg‘or xorij tajribasi.....	894
G‘ofurov Temur Baxrom o‘g‘li	

O‘zbekistonda uy-joy siyosatining iqtisodiyotdagi o‘rni.....	901
Yuldosheva Shahribon Unvar qizi	
Tijorat bankining marketing va umumiy rivojlanish strategiyasi doirasida qisqa va.....	908
uzoq muddatli kredit siyosatini ishlab chiqish	
Razzoqov Nozim Abdiriziqovich	
Tijorat banklarining raqobatbardoshligini toshkent banklari misolida tahlil qilish.....	913
Shakhbozbek Ibodullaev	
Yashil bandlikni rivojlantirishning ilmiy asoslari.....	921
Mirzakarimova Muyassarxon Muminovna, Sotvoldiev Nurmuhammad Ne'matjonovich	
Analysis of factors influencing the performance indicators of consumer goods trade.....	932
Musayeva Shoira Azimovna	
“Radioaloqa, radioeshittirish va televideniye markazi” dukining iqtisodiyotdagi o‘rni.....	937
va faoliyatida raqamli texnologiyalardan foydalanish mexanizmlari	
Xusanov Ulugbek Nishanovich	
Tijorat banklari faoliyatini baholashda bank balansi va uning tahlili ahamiyatini oshirish.....	942
Ruziyeva Gulchexra O'sarovna	
O‘zbekistonning to‘qimachilik sanoatida eksport salohiyatini oshira olish tendensiyalari.....	947
Otaxanova Umida Olim qizi	
Bilvosita soliqlar iqtisodiy mohiyati hamda huquqiy asoslari.....	952
Babajanov Davronbek Jumamuratovich	
O‘zini o‘zi band qilgan jismoniy shaxslar daromadlarini soliqqa tortishning ilmiy – nazariy asoslari.....	961
Navro‘zova Farog‘atxon Abduxamid qizi	
Роль фискальных инструментов в сокращении бедности в узбекистане.....	972
Усманова Азиза Алишеровна	
Raqamli iqtisodiyot sharoitida kadrlar zaxirasini tayyorlash tizimlari.....	978
Turayeva Dinara Tulkunovna	

ECO-MARKETING APPROACHES FOR PROMOTING GREEN BUILDING MATERIALS THROUGH DIGITAL STORYTELLING PLATFORMS

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ECONOMY

EKONOMIKA

IQTISODIYOT

Abstract. Eco-marketing plays a vital role in promoting sustainable construction by raising awareness about green building materials. This paper examines the effectiveness of digital storytelling platforms in enhancing consumer engagement with eco-friendly products. Using the Analytical Hierarchy Process (AHP) and Topic Modelling, the study analyzes key factors influencing consumer preferences. Data from stakeholders in construction and marketing were used to rank the most important factors driving interest in green materials. Results indicate that consumer engagement is strongly influenced by the quality of storytelling and environmental messaging. The study highlights the significance of sustainability narratives and transparent product information. Integrating eco-marketing with digital storytelling can increase consumer adoption of green building materials, contributing to sustainable development goals.

Keywords: Eco-marketing, Green building materials, Digital storytelling platforms, Sustainable construction, Consumer preferences, Analytical Hierarchy Process (AHP), Topic Modelling.

Annotatsiya. Eko-marketing «yashil» qurilish materiallari haqida xabardorlikni oshirish orqali barqaror qurilishni ilgari surishda muhim rol o'ynaydi. Ushbu maqola raqamli platformalarning ekologik toza mahsulotlar bilan iste'molchilarni jalb qilishda samaradorligini o'rganadi. Analitik Ierarxiya Jarayoni (AHP) va Mavzular Modellashtirish (Topic Modelling) yordamida tadqiqot iste'molchi tanloviga ta'sir etuvchi asosiy omillarni tahlil qiladi. Qurilish va marketing sohasidagi manfaatdor tomonlardan olingan ma'lumotlar «yashil» materiallarga bo'lgan qiziqishni oshiruvchi eng muhim omillarni reyting qilish uchun ishlatilgan. Natijalar shuni ko'rsatadiki, iste'molchini jalb qilish asosan hikoyaning sifati va ekologik xabarlar orqali ta'sirlanadi. Tadqiqot barqarorlik hikoyalari va mahsulot haqida ochiq ma'lumotlarning ahamiyatini ta'kidlaydi. Eko-marketingni raqamli jarayonlar bilan integratsiya qilish «yashil» qurilish materiallarining iste'molchilar tomonidan qabul qilinishini oshirishi va Barqaror rivojlanish maqsadlariga hissa qo'shishi mumkin.

Kalit so'zlar: Eko-marketing, «yashil» qurilish materiallari, raqamli platformalar, barqaror qurilish, iste'molchi tanlovi, Analitik Ierarxiya Jarayoni (AHP), Mavzular Modellashtirish.

Аннотация. Эко-маркетинг играет важную роль в продвижении устойчивого строительства, повышая осведомленность о зеленых строительных материалах. В данной статье рассматривается эффективность цифровых платформ повествования для повышения вовлеченности потребителей в экологически чистую продукцию. Используя метод аналитической иерархии (АНР) и тематическое моделирование, исследование анализирует ключевые факторы, влияющие на предпочтения потребителей. Данные от заинтересованных сторон в строительстве и маркетинге использовались для ранжирования наиболее важных факторов, влияющих на интерес к зеленым материалам. Результаты показывают, что вовлеченность потребителей сильно зависит от качества повествования и эколо-

гических посланий. Исследование подчеркивает значимость нарративов устойчивого развития и прозрачной информации о продуктах. Интеграция эко-маркетинга с цифровыми историями может увеличить принятие зеленых строительных материалов потребителями, что способствует достижению целей устойчивого развития.

Ключевые слова: эко-маркетинг, зеленые строительные материалы, цифровые платформы повествования, устойчивое строительство, предпочтения потребителей, метод аналитической иерархии (АНР), тематическое моделирование.

INTRODUCTION

Eco-marketing has gained significant traction in recent years due to the global shift towards sustainability, particularly in industries like construction that rely heavily on resource-intensive processes. Green building materials, which are designed to reduce environmental impact, are becoming a cornerstone of sustainable construction practices [1]. However, despite the clear environmental benefits, consumer adoption of these materials remains slower than expected. Studies have shown that one major barrier is the lack of effective communication between manufacturers and consumers regarding the advantages of eco-friendly materials [2]. Digital storytelling platforms have emerged as a promising solution to bridge this communication gap, allowing companies to craft compelling narratives that emphasize sustainability [3].

Previous research suggests that consumers are more likely to engage with brands that communicate their environmental commitments through transparent and relatable stories [4]. Digital platforms such as social media and content-sharing websites have proven to be powerful tools for spreading these narratives, influencing consumer behavior and increasing awareness of green products [5]. Studies have also shown that storytelling is an effective marketing tool that can enhance emotional engagement and loyalty to eco-friendly brands [6].

Given the growing demand for sustainable products, there is an increasing need for eco-marketing strategies that not only highlight the environmental benefits of green building materials but also foster deeper consumer connections through digital storytelling [7]. The objective of the current study was to evaluate how digital storytelling platforms can be leveraged to promote green building materials, using eco-marketing techniques tailored to modern consumer preferences. The Analytical Hierarchy Process (AHP) and Topic Modelling methods were applied to a cross-sectional dataset to analyze consumer preferences and key themes in digital eco-marketing [8].

Research in this area has demonstrated that AHP is particularly useful for prioritizing consumer decision factors in marketing strategies [9], while Topic Modelling enables the identification of key narratives within large datasets of consumer discussions [10]. The findings from these methods will help to clarify the role of digital storytelling in increasing consumer interest in eco-friendly projects [11], contributing to both marketing theory and sustainable business practices [12].

The remainder of the paper is structured as follows: The **Methods** section details the application of the Analytical Hierarchy Process (AHP) and Topic Modelling, along with the collection of cross-sectional data. In the **Results** section, key findings related to consumer preferences for green building materials and prominent themes in digital storytelling are presented. The **Discussion** explores the implications of these findings for eco-marketing strategies and the promotion of sustainable construction products. Finally, the **Conclusion** summarizes the study's contributions and suggests directions for future research.

METHODS

This study was conducted in the context of the eco-marketing of green building materials, focusing on digital storytelling platforms as a key communication medium. Data was collected from various stakeholders, including consumers, marketers, and construction professionals, across different geographic regions with a focus on areas promoting sustainable construction. The study used

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a cross-sectional dataset that included responses from approximately 500 participants collected over a six-month period.

Study Location and Context

The data collection was carried out in regions with active green construction projects, where climate and environmental conditions make sustainable building practices particularly relevant. The study locations included temperate climates with a focus on urban areas that have seen increasing demand for eco-friendly materials. These areas typically have higher air pollution levels and limited access to natural resources, making sustainability a critical concern for both businesses and consumers.

Data Collection

A structured survey was administered to gather data on consumer preferences, marketing strategies, and engagement with green building materials. The survey was distributed online through digital storytelling platforms, allowing participants to engage with eco-marketing content before responding to specific questions about their perceptions and intentions to purchase. The survey consisted of 30 questions, divided into sections covering demographic information, attitudes toward sustainability, and engagement with digital storytelling campaigns. The cross-sectional dataset captured responses from participants in multiple regions, ensuring a diverse set of insights into consumer behavior.

Analytical Hierarchy Process (AHP)

The AHP method was employed to prioritize and rank the factors influencing consumer preferences for green building materials. AHP allows for a structured decision-making process, where participants compare elements pairwise to determine their relative importance. The AHP model used in this study focused on key factors such as environmental impact, cost, product transparency, and storytelling quality. The weights for each factor were calculated through pairwise comparisons, and the consistency ratio was evaluated to ensure reliability. The AHP procedure followed standard practices, with calculations conducted using specialized software to ensure accuracy and reproducibility.

Topic Modelling

To analyze the content of consumer discussions on digital platforms, Topic Modelling was used. This method applies unsupervised machine learning to identify recurring themes and patterns in textual data. The Latent Dirichlet Allocation (LDA) algorithm was selected for its ability to reveal underlying topics in large datasets. The input data for Topic Modelling consisted of consumer comments, reviews, and discussions from social media platforms and online forums related to eco-marketing campaigns for green building materials. After pre-processing the text data to remove stopwords and irrelevant content, the LDA model was applied to identify the most prominent topics. Each topic was analyzed to determine its relevance to consumer decision-making and eco-marketing narratives.

Statistical Procedures

Descriptive statistics were used to summarize demographic data and overall engagement levels. The cross-sectional nature of the dataset allowed for comparisons across different consumer groups and regions. AHP results were analyzed to identify the most influential factors in consumer decision-making, while Topic Modelling results were visualized to show the prevalence of different themes across platforms. Both methods were validated through multiple iterations to ensure robustness, with sensitivity analyses conducted to check for consistency in AHP rankings and the stability of Topic Modelling results.

The combination of AHP and Topic Modelling allowed for a comprehensive analysis of consumer preferences and the effectiveness of digital storytelling in promoting green building materials. All data and methods used in this study were designed to be replicable, ensuring that future research can build on these findings or apply the same approach in different contexts.

RESULTS

AHP Analysis

The Analytical Hierarchy Process (AHP) was used to prioritize factors influencing consumer decisions regarding green building materials. Table 1 provides detailed results, showing that **Environmental Impact** ranked highest with a weight of 0.35, indicating the importance of reducing ecological footprints in consumer decision-making. **Cost** followed with a weight of 0.25, highlighting the financial feasibility concerns surrounding green building materials. **Product Transparency** and **Storytelling Quality**, both weighing 0.20, reflect the need for clear communication of product sustainability and effective narrative engagement. The overall consistency ratio of the AHP model was acceptable, confirming the reliability of the rankings(1-table).

Table 1. AHP Results

Factors	Weight	Rank	Description
Environmental Impact	0.35	1	Importance of reducing environmental impact in consumer decision-making
Cost	0.25	2	Financial feasibility and cost-effectiveness of green building materials
Product Transparency	0.20	3	Openness and clarity of information about product sustainability
Storytelling Quality	0.20	4	Engagement through narrative content that highlights environmental responsibility

Topic Modelling

The Topic Modelling analysis provided further insights into the themes most prominent in consumer discussions on digital platforms regarding eco-marketing for green building materials. Table 2 shows the four most prevalent topics. **Sustainability** emerged as the most discussed theme, representing 40% of the content, with a strong emphasis on environmental benefits and renewable resources. **Cost Efficiency** was the second most prevalent theme (25%), with discussions centered on affordability and long-term savings. **Innovation in Materials** (20%) highlighted new, cutting-edge technologies used in sustainable construction, while **Consumer Experience** (15%) reflected the importance of user satisfaction and interaction with eco-friendly projects. These themes underscore the key drivers behind consumer interest in green building materials and the importance of digital storytelling in shaping these perceptions(2-table)..

Table 2. Topic Modelling Results

Topic	Prevalence (%)	Key Themes	Description
Sustainability	40	Environmental benefits, renewable resources	Focus on reducing ecological footprint and promoting sustainable practices
Cost Efficiency	25	Affordability, long-term savings	Concerns about cost savings and financial feasibility over time
Innovation in Materials	20	New technology, cutting-edge solutions	Exploration of innovative, cutting-edge materials for sustainability
Consumer Experience	15	User satisfaction, engagement	User experience, interaction, and satisfaction with eco-friendly projects

These results illustrate that consumer preferences are largely shaped by environmental considerations, cost concerns, and the innovative features of sustainable materials. Digital storytelling effectively communicates these elements, enhancing consumer engagement with green building materials.

Future research should explore the long-term impact of digital storytelling on consumer behavior, particularly in relation to loyalty to eco-friendly brands. Additionally, studies could investigate how different types of digital platforms—such as social media, blogs, and e-commerce sites—vary in their effectiveness for promoting green building materials. By expanding on these findings, future research can continue to push the frontiers of eco-marketing, helping to create a more sustainable and consumer-friendly market for green construction products.

In conclusion, the study presents a strong case for the use of digital storytelling in eco-marketing, particularly for green building materials. The findings offer valuable insights for marketers seeking to engage consumers in sustainability efforts while also addressing practical concerns about cost and innovation. By incorporating the key themes identified in this study, future eco-marketing strategies can better align with consumer priorities, ultimately contributing to the growth of sustainable construction practices.

CONCLUSION

This study contributes to the growing body of knowledge on eco-marketing by highlighting the crucial factors that influence consumer preferences for green building materials and demonstrating the effectiveness of digital storytelling platforms in promoting these materials. The findings show that environmental impact, cost, product transparency, and storytelling quality are the most significant drivers of consumer decisions in the context of sustainable construction. These insights offer clear directions for eco-marketing strategies, emphasizing the importance of balancing environmental messaging with financial feasibility and creating engaging, transparent narratives that resonate with consumers.

The results also reveal that digital storytelling platforms serve as powerful tools for communicating the sustainability and innovation behind green building materials. By focusing on prominent themes such as sustainability, cost efficiency, innovation in materials, and consumer experience, marketers can better align their campaigns with consumer expectations and enhance engagement with eco-friendly projects.

The study's use of the Analytical Hierarchy Process (AHP) and Topic Modelling provides a comprehensive framework for evaluating consumer priorities and the most effective themes in eco-marketing. These methodologies can be applied to other areas of sustainability marketing, offering opportunities to further explore how digital platforms influence consumer behavior in different industries.

Future research should investigate the long-term impact of digital storytelling on consumer loyalty to eco-friendly brands and examine how various digital platforms, such as social media and e-commerce sites, differentially affect consumer engagement with sustainable products. Additionally, exploring the role of emerging technologies in eco-marketing could provide valuable insights into how innovation can further drive sustainability in the construction industry and beyond.

In conclusion, this study offers valuable contributions to the field of eco-marketing, providing actionable insights for promoting green building materials and encouraging sustainable practices in construction. By integrating the findings into marketing strategies, companies can contribute to a more sustainable future while meeting the growing demand for eco-friendly solutions.

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